

PROTEIN THROUGH FOOD PRODUCTS PRODUCTION IN THE ORGANIZATION.

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ABSTRACT: This article is about the question that is considered urgent nowadays, that is, the irreplaceable role of proteins in the preparation of food products as high-molecular, nitrogen-containing organic substances.

KEY WORDS: Proteins, molecular, amino acids, proteins, carbon, biocatalytic, amino acids. A living organism is distinguished by the high order of its structural components and the fact that it has a unique structural structure that ensures the occurrence of various biological functions, such as phenotypic processes. Proteins play a decisive role in the unity of the structural and functional order of organisms, which is the essence of life, and they cannot be replaced by other groups of organic compounds.

Proteins are high-molecular, nitrogen-containing organic substances, their molecules are composed of amino acid residues. They play an important role in the structural structure and functions of the cell, because genetic information is transferred with their help. Otherwise, they are called proteins (Greek, "protos" – "primary", "important"). In fact, proteins are primary for living organisms both in terms of quantitative indicators and in terms of their importance in the body. In animals, protein makes up 40-50% or more of dry mass, while in plants it is less than 1% to 16%. in bacteria, viruses and yeast it ranges from 13% to 99% (Table 3).

The amount of protein in the dry matter residue of some organisms. Table 1.

Organizm turi	Type of organism Average protein content (in %)
Human and animal organism	45-70
Fish	40-47
Herbaceous plants	9-16
Trees	1-2

Bacteria	50-93
Viruses	81-99
Yeast	31-62
Mold fungus	13-43

As can be seen from Table 1, the amount of protein in plants is quite low, but the amount of protein is high in the parts of the plant that grow rapidly and have a strong metabolism. Proteins have a number of properties that are not characteristic of other organic compounds. These properties are related to the functions of proteins that ensure the manifestation of their vital processes. These features include: - the infinite diversity of its structure and, at the same time, its peculiarity;

- great variety of physical and chemical changes;
- the ability to interact within the cell;
- the ability to respond to external influences by changing the molecular configuration and restore the initial state when the influence ends;
- tendency to interact with other chemical compounds by forming complexes and structures;
- the presence of biocatalytic and other properties.

As for the elemental composition of proteins of living organisms, in terms of quantity, they are as follows: carbon 50.0-55.0%; hydrogen 6.5-7.3%; nitrogen 15.0-18.0%; oxygen 21.0-24.0%; sulfur 0.0-20.54%; ash residue 0.0-0.5%.

Polypeptides with a molecular weight of up to 6000 Da are called peptides, and those with a molecular weight of 6000 Da and more are called proteins. Theoretically, if two dipeptides are formed from two amino acids, 24 tetrapeptides can be obtained from four, and $2.4 \cdot 10^{18}$ isomers can be obtained from 20 proteinogenic amino acids. According to scientists, there are 3,000 different proteins in the E.coli organism, while according to L. Pauling's calculations, the number of proteins in humans is about 100,000. But recent studies prove that this figure is much higher.

It is known that the proteins in the tissues and organs of humans, animals, plants and microorganisms are fundamentally different from each other, they have species-specific properties. The protein of another organism, for example, the protein of hen's egg, introduced into the animal's blood, has a toxic effect on it.

Proteins differ not only in their amino acid composition, but also in their sequence in the molecule. Protein substances taken with food do not directly enter the internal environment of the body, but pass through the digestive

organs, they are broken down into amino acids, and then they no longer have species specificity. Amino acids absorbed into the blood, later in the tissues, are included in the composition of proteins specific to a particular organism. Nowadays, it has been found that there are different aspects in the chemical structure of proteins that perform the same biological function in different animal species. Proteins of different tissues and organs of the body also have their own special features. This type of specificity is explained by the existence of a difference in the structure of proteins, as well as the function of certain tissues and organs.

CONCLUSION In the formation of proteins in the body through food products, the proteins received in the body through plant and animal products are absorbed into the blood, and then in the tissues, they are included in the necessary proteins that are unique to a particular organism, as a result, the body itself produces the protein it needs

List of references:

1. G. Gafin biochemistry and molecular biology textbook © SamSU Publisher 2021.
2. D. Nelson, M. Cox. Basic biochemistry Lenindjera. -Moscow, BINOM. Laboratory science, 2011.
3. TOrakulov Yo.H. Biochemistry and molecular biology. - Tashkent. "Uzbekistan", 1996.
4. Valikhanov M.N., Dalimova S.N., Umarova G.B., P.Mirkhamidova,
5. Biological chemistry and molecular biology (part 2 Molecular biology). - Tashkent, "NavrOz" 2015
6. Tashkent, "NavrOz" 2015
7. M.N. Valikhanov, Biochemistry Tashkent. "University". 2009.
8. M. N. Valikhonov. Biochemistry. Tashkent: 2010. O. Oripov, A. O. Nasrullayev. Bioorganic chemistry. Tashkent 2012

